

Pharmaceutical Marketing: Theory and Practice by Medical Representatives

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ABSTRACT

This article comes in a series that aims at an assessment of knowledge and application of marketing concepts of medical representatives in Pune, India, using a survey questionnaire. Descriptive hypotheses were set and studied based on primary data collected from 100 medical representatives based in Pune who were surveyed from different pharmaceutical companies on the awareness and application of marketing concepts in their actual work. Both knowledge and application were measured on a 5-point Likert scale for responses to 10 items under each of the variables. Sample means were compared against the hypothesized population means of the scale midpoints of 2 and were tested for statistical significance at the 95 % confidence level. The study revealed that both the sample means for knowledge and application were statistically significant, albeit, on opposite sides. While the knowledge mean was found to be well above the hypothesized population mean, the application level mean was found to be considerably lower than the hypothesized population mean. The total knowledge level was found to be statistically significant (Mean = 3.22; SD = 0.89), the total application level was found to be low at (Mean= 1.51; SD = 0.76). The results of the study show that the medical representatives, though quite well aware of the marketing concepts to be utilized by them, but use their application skills poorly, which are also confirmed by the literature especially regarding their unethical practices prevalent in present times.

KEYWORDS: Medical representatives, Marketing practices, Awareness, Application.

1. INTRODUCTION

Medical Representatives are appointed by the pharmaceutical companies to provide knowledge to the medical fraternity about their products in terms of place and price. They have a multifactorial role: along with their designated role as listed in the WHO, as promoters of drugs to the medical community they also play a part as sales agents as they are a between the company distributors and retailers (Rao, 1998). Ideally, they are supposed to have in-depth knowledge in terms of clinical trials and research of the drugs with regards to the disease in question and must be able to supply relevant information and satisfy the queries of the medical guild (The Drug Rep: Historical Background, 2007).

Every pharmaceutical company trains about 2500 to 8000 medical representatives to promote and sell medicines. In return for boosting the company's sales targets they, along with their salary they are incentivized with trips abroad, increments in salary, promotion, etc. (Goyal and Pareek, 2013).

Quite the reverse to providing information ethically to the medical fraternity, they in the name of marketing strategies for self-gain, indulge in ambiguous information, incentives which range from booking free seminars, sponsorships in India and abroad, gifts and unethical trade by asking the doctors to prescribe their brand of medicines to boost the sales of the company in return for their inducements (Goyal and Pareek, 2013).

This research paper seeks to explore the marketing knowledge and its application by medical representatives in Pune, India. The research question to be addressed is as follows:

RQ: Do the medical representatives from Pune, India, show reasonable knowledge and its application of the marketing concepts?

The term "reasonable" was operationalized at the midpoint of a 5-point Likert scale at the value of $(0+1+2+3+4)/5=2$, with 0 indicating Not at all aware/Not at all used and 4 indicating Highly aware/Widely used.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In India, the pharmaceutical industry has more than 7000 drugs (Bhatt, 1992) and counting, to date, which are promoted by an army of eighty thousand medical representatives (Goyal and Pareek 2013). An average prescription written by doctors in India may range up to 600 rupees (Goyal and Pareek 2013) as branded medicines, aggressively promoted by medical representatives in India, have an advantage over lower-priced generic drugs. An average pharmaceutical company in the UK spends at least 200 million pounds since 1985 (Goyal and Pareek, 2013) and the US spent 20.4 million dollars since 2004 i.e. 35% on total promotional activity by medical representatives (Al-Areefi *et al.*, 2013). Pharmaceutical marketing concepts are different as it targets both doctors and its medical representatives for the supply and purchase of its medicines and formulations giving rise to an element of wrong practices among all the concerned stakeholders.

A study in Yemen found that the medical coterie agrees to meet the medical representatives not only for scientific knowledge for free samples, gifts (Al-Areefi *et al.*, 2013) and similar scenarios in India, where doctors look for freebies in return to prescribing for the brands promoted by the medical representatives. A study conducted by Mukattash *et al.*, (2017), elicited that medical representatives from MNC (Multinational companies had a better statistically significant scientific knowledge base with regards to randomized control trials (42%) than the local companies. More than forty percent of them do not understand terms like Confidence Interval, study phases, placebo/sham trials (47%). 66.5 % do understand that knowledge of clinical trials and important aspects of the drug research and seventy percent agree that their company does take an effort in providing them with the relevant training.

In their defense, they claim that failure to apply these principles is due to that barrier like the following which comes in the way of implementation of the ethical marketing concepts: the notion that the medical fraternity is too busy to listen to them (52.5%); lack of research training (52%); lack of confidence to explain the clinical trials and research to the doctors (37%); trying for better relationships with the doctors to promote and increase prescriptions rather than spend time educating them about the drugs (45%). In Jordan, the medical representatives have to be licensed pharmacists (Mukattash *et al* 2017) and this information is in contrast to Indian medical representatives who at times not pharmacy graduates, but smart graduates who learn on the job and therefore they lack relevant scientific knowledge. On the other hand, the medical representatives have put forth their point that they have to follow the dictates of the shareholders of the company and are asked to influence the physicians using social psychology tactics like social proof principles: Reciprocation, social proof, liking, commitment, authority, scarcity, etc. to influence the already overburdened and stressed physicians at a subconscious level by offering gifts and incentives (Patwardhan, 2016).

A study was done in Ahmedabad (Bhatnagar And Mishra, 2010), on the emotional quotient of medical representatives showed that emotional dissonance (discord or lack of harmony) among MR's is negatively correlated to their emotional wellbeing and organizational identity (organizational identity is to infuse the employees with motivation and feeling and helps the employees to cope with stress) and gives rise to a higher likelihood of the employee's feelings of discord and want to leave the company as they experience reduced emotional support. The study also elaborates that sales activity is a key objective of the pharmaceutical companies the HR has to spruce up its role to support the employee's issues of emotional dissonance at work to enhance their quality of service. A contextual research gap exists and hence this study was undertaken by surveying medical representatives.

3. METHODOLOGY

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 100 medical representatives (Bullen, 2016).
2. The selection of the 100 medical representatives was based on the judgment of the writer of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenience sampling was used.
3. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts: a. Assessment of marketing conceptual knowledge and b. Assessment of concepts practiced.

4. 10 concepts were framed and responses were sought on Likert-scales in two sections: knowledge level and practice level.
5. For assessment of knowledge levels the scale used was: 0-Not at all aware, 1-Little bit aware, 2-Somewhat aware, 3-Well aware, 4-Highly aware for ten concepts:
 - i. Product life cycle,
 - ii. 4Ps of marketing,
 - iii. Ethics in Marketing,
 - iv. Physician's sample utilization strategy to generate prescriptions,
 - v. Fieldwork strategy,
 - vi. Strategies for Individual doctor's sponsorships,
 - vii. Diversified strategy,
 - viii. Prescribing behaviour,
 - ix. Networking skills,
 - x. Difference between marketing and selling (Kotler and Armstrong 2010).
6. For assessment of practical application levels the scale used was: 0-Not at all used, 1-Used a little bit, 2-Used somewhat, 3-Used well, 4-Used widely of the ten concepts as listed in point 5 earlier.
7. T-test was used at the 95% confidence level and the sample mean was tested for statistical significance by comparing it with a hypothesized population mean taken at mid-point of the scales $(0+1+2+3+4)/5=2$ connoting an event by chance
8. Data analysis includes a descriptive analysis specifying features of the sample and inferential analysis to test the hypotheses. A t-test is used given the fact that the SD of the population is not known, in which case, a Z-test could have been applied. The use of a t-test in practice is widely done as a substitute for the Z-test wherein the SD of the sample is taken as the SD of the population (given unknown population SD).

3.1 Statement of hypotheses

H₀₁: The knowledge level about marketing concepts is reasonable.

H_{a1}: The knowledge level about marketing concepts is better than reasonable.

H₀₂: These concepts are applied in practice as well at a reasonable level.

H_{a2}: These concepts in practice are not applied at a reasonable level.

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.899 that is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered as reliable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive analysis

Male Medical Representatives (94) dominated the sample as compared to females (6). Most of them belonged to the age group > 40 years (34) and 40-50 years. Most of the representatives had at least fifteen years of experience and worked for Indian companies (59).

4.2 Inferential analysis

The null hypotheses were set as the sample mean (\bar{x}) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). Summary of the ratings for the awareness levels is given in Table 1 below:

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average knowledge rating	3.3	3.23	3.14	3.18	3.32	3.16	3.13	3.2	3.32	3.17	3.22

Summary of the ratings for the application levels is given in Table 2 below:

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average application rating	1.45	1.40	1.45	1.62	1.60	1.49	1.32	1.58	1.65	1.51	1.51

Table 3 shows the testing of the two hypotheses at the 95% confidence level.

Parameter	H1 value	H2 value
Sample Mean (\bar{x})	3.22	1.51
The hypothesized population mean (μ)	2.00	2.00
SD of sample	0.86	0.76
n (sample size)	100	100
t-value= $\text{abs}((\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n}))$	13.78	6.45
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t,(n-1),1)$	0.00000	0.00000
Decision	Reject Null	Reject Null

Both the null hypotheses were rejected in favour of the alternate that the sample means are significantly different from the hypothesized population means.

The sample mean for knowledge was 3.22 (SD = 0.88) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly higher than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2. Interestingly, the sample mean for the application was only 1.51 (SD = 0.76) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly lower than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2. The gap between the knowledge mean of 3.22 and the application mean of 1.51 is 1.71 which is more than fifty percent of the knowledge level.

5. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that medical representative's despite being quite well aware of the marketing concepts concerning their arena of work; use their application skills poorly, which are also confirmed by the literature especially regarding their unethical practices prevalent in present times. The pharmaceutical companies must take note of the practices of their representatives and instill ethical standards for the promotion and sales of drugs. As this study is based on a convenient sample generalizability of the results in terms of external validity may be an issue that can be improved upon by using other study design with larger multicentre studies.

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